

**D4.4 Advancing the
collaboration in
Personalised Medicine
between Africa and
Europe, achieved results
and impacts.**

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Advancing the collaboration in Personalised Medicine between Africa and Europe, achieved results and impacts of the EU-Africa PerMed project.

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document summarises the EU-Africa PerMed major achievements, described as both results and impacts.

After a short introduction to the project, with main objectives and the planned work packages, the document presents the project log frame, to graphically show the linkage between the different Work packages that formed the project workplan, main objectives and all the activities sought to contribute to the impacts set forth in the proposal. The project had the following expected impacts:

- Integrating the country/group of countries into ICPeMed activities
- Support wider adoption of standards developed in Europe
- Support the EU-AU policy dialogues relevant to research and health
- Contribute towards the UN Sustainable Development Goal 3: Ensure healthy lives and promote well-being for all at all ages.

A section is included which presents the expected outcomes and impacts as they were initially outlined in the project proposal, explaining how far the project has been able to achieve them. It also includes the metrics for the Key Performance Indicators that were selected to be used to measure the performance of the project in achieving the expected impacts. **EU-Africa PerMed performance has been very good in terms of achieving the expected impacts, highlighting that thanks to the project work, four African organisations from South Africa, Egypt, Tunisia and Tanzania are now full members of ICPeMed.**

The document also reviews all the project results and impacts. It is not always easy to differentiate what are direct results (outputs) from the project and what are the effects and changes that the project activity and/or results may have had, on short term (outcomes) and long term (impacts). In many cases, the impacts are not easy to record at this time and make take place after the end of the project, such as for example of changes in national health polices to advance in PM implementation or new programmes and calls related to PM that may support the collaboration between African and Europe. The report describes the main project achievements, results and impacts, grouped based on the typology of the impact:

- Scientific impact. Advancing knowledge: mapping and describing the African PM landscape
- Policy and scientific impact. Exchange with stakeholders and identification of needs and common interests
- Policy and scientific impact: The EU-Africa PerMed Action Plan
- Policy impact: Integration of African countries In ICPeMed
- Scientific and capacity building impact: Creating international scientific networks and advancing young researchers' careers
- Policy and social impact: raising awareness about PM in Africa and the importance of international collaboration

An important project output has been the **EU-Africa PerMed Actions Plan**, developed through extensive input from Consortium members and the Advisory Board, and validated with external stakeholders. The document presents an Action Plan to facilitate, foster and promote collaboration in the field of Personalised Medicine (PM) between Africa and Europe. It includes 26 concrete PM research activities and supporting activities formulated as recommendations to be implemented at different levels and by different actors, to achieve the objectives set forth by the project:

- Foster, facilitate and encourage joint PM activities, projects and programmes between Africa and Europe,

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- Strengthen bilateral European Union and African Union (EU-AU) science, technology and innovation (STI) relations in the area of health, including PM.

Raising awareness about PM and the importance of international collaboration has been a key objective throughout the project, that has served to not only promote the participation of African organisations in ICPeMed, but also to advance the PM agenda in African countries and regions. All the stakeholder engagement activities have contributed somehow to this important objective, as well as the project participating in external events or producing relevant policy documents, such as the two policy briefs and the Dakar Declaration on Europe- Africa collaboration in Personalised Medicine, or the active communication in social networks.

Finally, the document includes a section on some project additional impacts not initially foreseen in the proposal that are relevant to show, such as contributing to advancing the PM agenda, at national, regional and Pan-African level. Some examples are briefly explained for Kenya and Tunisia. Project activities, not initially planned, have also contributed to advancing the PM agenda in Africa, or references of EU-Africa PerMed work by third parties.

The project has also had some positive impacts/effects on European members states and on individual organisations that have participated in the project. We present the example of France (with two organisations participating as partners in the project, ANR and INSERM) and the African Population Health Research Centre (APHRC).

The different results and variety of impacts of the project show how Coordination and Support Actions (CSA) such as EU-Africa PerMed can have many measurable short-term effects as well as broader and long-term effects. It shows the value of networking and cooperation when it comes to support and strengthen international research collaborations, and how research support actions such as the CSAs funded by the EU Research Framework Programmes are valuable instruments to do so.

EU-Africa PerMed has provided the grounds for a stronger and more sustainable Africa-Europe cooperation in PM. It has created favourable contexts and opportunities for networking and discussion, to share concepts and ideas and for all major stakeholders to be convinced of the gains that this collaboration has for both parts, Africa and Europe.

1) INTRODUCTION

EU-Africa PerMed started its journey in February 2021, with the COVID19 pandemic still around, challenging the world and making us more aware of how vulnerable we are and how important it is to collaborate internationally in health and biomedical research. The EU-Africa PerMed project, funded by the EC Horizon 2020 programme¹, made it possible for a group of 13 partners from Africa and Europe to start working together with the aim of strengthening the collaboration between both regions to advance in Personalised Medicine (PM) research, innovation and implementation. A big challenge but also a big responsibility, as the results of our work should have a positive impact, at the end, on improving people's health and wellbeing.

The **EU-Africa PerMed** project's main aim included, as an important objective, to integrate African countries into ICPeMed (International Consortium of Personalised Medicine). This will help foster joint Personalised Medicine (PM) projects and programmes between Europe and Africa, strengthen bilateral EU-AU Science, Technology and Innovation (STI) relations in the area of health and therefore contribute to a successful implementation of PM in the global context. The project has brought together Stakeholders from Europe and various regions of Africa, dialogues and discussions have been facilitated to understand the gaps and guide policy for PM. On the long run, incorporating African countries in the global PM agenda will ensure equity by reducing health disparities between developed and developing countries, as well as facilitate access of African countries to new tools and technologies that have the potential to make healthcare more efficient to better tackle the growing global burden of infectious diseases and non-infectious diseases.

During a period of 54 months, the EU-Africa PerMed consortium has worked towards fostering a stronger global collaboration in PM through the umbrella of ICPeMed, and by this, to better tackle global health challenges such as infectious diseases and future pandemics.

The EU-Africa PerMed project was designed and planned to have in mind the expected impacts listed in the H2020 topic description², which were:

- Integrating the country/group of countries into ICPeMed activities
- Support wider adoption of standards developed in Europe
- Support the EU-AU policy dialogues relevant to research and health
- Contribute towards the UN Sustainable Development Goal 3: Ensure healthy lives and promote well-being for all at all ages.

The topic description stated that: *The action should focus on building links with third countries by analysing the potential and advantages of collaboration in personalised medicine (PM) with those countries, studying areas of interest for Europe in PM collaboration and promoting international standards in the field. In particular the uptake of personalised approaches in health systems and healthcare should be addressed, taking into account social, cultural, ethical and legal aspects, health economy issues and equitable healthcare.* For the 2020 call, the project should focus on countries in Africa, linking also into the EU-AU (African Union) policy dialogue and considering the new Africa-Europa Alliance for Sustainable investment and Jobs.

This deliverable describes what have been the main results and the effects/impacts it has had on research, on policy, on capacity building and on changing the mindset of PM in African countries, as well as on the project participants, both at individual and institutional level.

¹ EU-Africa PerMed has been funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement Number 964333. (<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/964333>)

² The project was funded responding to the specific SC1-HCO-01-2018-2019-2020: Actions in support of the International Consortium for Personalised Medicine/International aspects (Horizon 2020 Work Programme 2018-2020. 8. Health, demographic change and wellbeing)

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2) THE EU-AFRICA PerMed PROJECT

Incorporating African countries in the global PM research agenda will contribute to shortening the existing health disparities, as well as facilitating the access of African countries to new tools and technologies that have the potential to make healthcare more efficient and equitable. An International Consortium for Personalised Medicine (ICPerMed) was launched in 2016, bringing together already more than 50 health research funders, ministries and policy-making organisations, to coordinate research and health policy to advance together the implementation of PM. While the majority of members are still coming from Europe, the consortium has the vision of being international and open to incorporating members from all world regions,

In order to support the objective of encouraging the integration of non-EU countries in ICPerMed, the **EU-Africa PerMed project** was funded by the EU Horizon 2020 programme and supports the integration of African countries into ICPerMed activities as a means to contribute to a successful implementation of PM in the global context, fostering specifically joint PM projects and programmes between Europe and Africa, as well as strengthening bilateral EU-AU science, technology and innovation (STI) relations in the area of health.

The project was launched in February 2021 and implemented by a consortium of 13 partners, 6 from Europe and 7 Africa, shown in the figure below:

Figure 1: The EU-Africa PerMed consortium

The consortium is supported by an Advisory Board of 5 members, all of them with expertise in international research collaboration and funding, health research and PM in African and European contexts.

More information about the consortium and the Advisory Board are available on the project website (<https://www.euafrica-permed.eu/>).

Through four and a half years³, the consortium worked towards fostering a stronger global collaboration in PM through the umbrella of ICPerMed, and by this, to better tackle global health challenges such as infectious diseases and future pandemics. As the COVID pandemic showed, addressing global health challenges is only possible by building and strengthening international, inter-continental and national scientific cooperation between scientists, decision/policy makers, private practitioners, industries and health professional and civil

³ EU Africa PerMed was granted a 6 month no cost extension, and the project finished on 31st July of 2025

society, The EU-Africa PerMed project has worked towards supporting and strengthening this cooperation between Africa and Europe.

THE EU-AFRICA PerMed workplan

Figure 2: The EU-Africa PerMed workplan

3) THE EU-AFRICA PerMed LOGFRAME

The following figure shows the project logic framework, which summarise the main project elements (objectives, activities, results and impacts) and how they interact. It presents how the different project activities carried out in the different work packages have all contributed to the results and project impacts.

It helps to visualise the main project activities and evaluate the results and how far the project has achieved the expected impacts already at the end of its runtime.

EU-AFRICA PerMed had the main goal to strengthen the collaboration between Africa and Europe in Personalised Medicine research and to integrate African organisations in ICPeMed.

Through the different Work packages that formed the project workplan, the consortium has worked towards achieving this main goal, and all the activities sought to contribute to the impacts set forth in the proposal, as it can be seen in Figure 1.

EU-AFRICA PerMed LOGIC FRAMEWORK

PROJECT GOAL to strengthen the collaboration of both regions in PM R&I activities, integrate African countries into ICPeMed activities, support wider adoption of international standards and contribute to support the EU-AU policy dialogue relevant to research and health

Figure 3: The EU-Africa PerMed log frame

4) THE EU-AFRICA PerMed EXPECTED IMPACTS

As stated in the Description of Action of the project (Annex B to the Gran Agreement signed with the EC), the project was designed and planned with the aim of achieving the expected impacts listed in the topic description.

1. Integrating the country/group of countries into ICPeMed activities
2. Support wider adoption of standards developed in Europe
3. Support the EU-AU policy dialogues relevant to research and health
4. Contribute towards the UN Sustainable Development Goal 3: *Ensure healthy lives and promote well-being for all at all ages.*

The first expected impact can be considered as a short-term impact, as it can be directly achieved by the project within the timeframe of its duration and evidence of its achievement can be presented as a final result of the project. For the impacts 2 and 3, the project planned activities and actions that sought to work towards both impacts, contributing as much as possible and within the capacities of the project to them. But in both cases, although the contribution of the project has been very important, it has to be seen as one of the many other ongoing projects, actions and initiatives that are also contributing to these impacts. For this, the direct evidence of both these impacts will be presented in terms of productive interactions carried out within the duration of the project. For the last expected impact, a much more long-term impact, the project aims at integrating African countries in the global PM agenda, so that all countries can benefit of the opportunities that PM brings to improve the health of the population. This achievement is not within the capacity of the **EU-Africa PerMed** project, so the contribution to it may be measured by the full achievement of impact n° 1.

Summarised below are the impacts listed in the topic and key performance indicators to measures success, with the results obtained by the project.

SHORT-TERM IMPACTS: INTEGRATING THE COUNTRY/GROUP OF COUNTRIES INTO ICPeMed		
KEY PERFORMANCE INDICATORS	TARGET	RESULT
Number of organisations joining the ICPeMed consortium at the end of the project	<i>at least 3</i>	4
Number of African organisations participating in ICPeMed activities	<i>at least 6</i>	7
Number of bilateral meetings with African organisations to explain the ICPeMed	<i>at least 10</i>	15 organisations, in many cases more than one bilateral meeting
Number of African organisations participating in ERA PerMed future calls Note. The last call of ERA PerMed was launched in 2022	<i>at least 2</i>	ASRT (Egypt) and SAMRC (South Africa)
Number of EU-Africa PerMed meetings with ICPeMed participation	<i>at least 3</i>	6
MEDIUM-TERM IMPACTS: SUPPORT WIDER ADOPTION OF STANDARDS DEVELOPED IN EUROPE		
KEY PERFORMANCE INDICATORS	TARGET	RESULT
Number of training courses performed	<i>at least 3</i>	2 summer schools and 11 webinars
Number of participants in each of the on-site training activities	<i>target: 20-30</i>	1 st summer school: 35 2 nd Summer school: 38
Number of participants of the online training	<i>target: at least 50</i>	In total, 1284 people registered to join the online webinars
MEDIUM-TERM IMPACTS: SUPPORT THE EU-AU POLICY DIALOGUES RELEVANT TO RESEARCH AND HEALTH		
Key Performance Indicators	TARGET	RESULT
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Number of meetings/activities with African stakeholders 	<i>at least 3</i>	3 stakeholder workshops EDCTP 10 th Forum/Scientific symposium 4 African regional meetings 1 ICPeMed engagement meeting African Health Funders Forum

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Number of meetings with actors involved in the EU-AU policy dialogue 	<p><i>target: at least 3.</i></p>	<p>EU-AU Summit, Science and Innovation Dedicated session on PM (Feb2022) AU-EU Innovation Agenda Stakeholder Event (Nov22) World Science Forum (Dec22) EU Spanish Presidency event in Valencia (Oct 2023) World Health Summit 2024 AU-EU Innovation Agenda workshop on Public Health (Dec2024)</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Number and type of documents prepared and shared 	<p><i>target, at least 3.</i></p>	<p>2 Policy Briefs 1 Action Plan</p>
<p>LONG TERM IMPACT: Contribute towards the UN Sustainable Development Goal 3: Ensure healthy lives and promote well-being for all at all ages.</p>		
<p>EXPECTED IMPACT</p>		
<p><i>HOW EU-Africa PerMed has contributed</i></p>		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Integrating four African organisations in ICPeMed and one in EP PerMed. Increasing the knowledge and understanding among African Ministries of health, Ministries of Education and science, Research funders, academia, clinicians and the general public on the opportunities that PM offers to optimise prevention, diagnosis and treatment of diseases and advancing the uptake of PM in healthcare. Supporting the creation of AU-EU scientific networks interested in PM collaborative projects, Advancing the creation of regional/national PM focus groups in Africa. Contributing to raise awareness and knowledge among Africa policy makers of the benefits of PM and why it is important that Africa does not lose the possibility of benefiting of incorporating genomic testing and technologies in important areas such as: Adverse Drug Reactions (ADRs), Rare and Genetic disease, Sickle-Cell Disease, Cancer, Disease outbreak and response surveillance. to build capacity, strengthen local expertise, and foster international partnerships. 		

5) EU-AFRICA PerMed MAIN ACHIEVEMENTS, RESULTS AND IMPACTS

Presented below are main results and impacts coming from the EU-Africa PerMed project. It is not always easy to differentiate what are direct results (outputs) from the project and what are the effects and changes that the project activity and/or results may have had, on short term (outcomes) and long term (impacts). In many cases, the impacts are not easy to record at this time and may take place after the end of the project, such as for example of changes in national health polices to advance in PM implementation or new programmes and calls related to PM that may support the collaboration between African and Europe.

What is normally possible is to recall the activities that have been carried out by the project and that are contributing and helping to achieve expected /and unexpected outcomes and impacts. These are normally based, in the case of EU-Africa PerMed, of productive interactions with relevant stakeholders that have the capacity to make changes. The project has devoted much effort to this, through stakeholder engagement workshops, and also through training and capacity building activities and the interaction with policy makers and ongoing programmes and initiatives. All this activity has been summarised in the previous part of this report and in some of the project deliverables and reporting documents.

In this section, we describe the main project results and outcomes, grouped based on the typology of the typology of expected impact:

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1. **Scientific impact.** Advancing knowledge: mapping and describing the African PM landscape; Integrating African funding organisations in ERA PerMed (funding activities).
2. **Policy and scientific impact.** Exchange with stakeholders and identification of needs and common interests
3. **Policy and scientific impact:** The EU-Africa PerMed Action Plan
4. **Policy impact:** Integration of African countries In ICPeMed and ERA PerMed.
5. **Scientific and capacity building impact:** Creating international scientific networks and advancing young researchers' careers
6. **Policy and social impact:** raising awareness about PM in Africa and the importance of international collaboration

5.1 ADVANCING KNOWLEDGE: MAPPING AND DESCRIBING THE AFRICAN PM LANDSCAPE

KEY OUTPUT (WP2)

Mapping the Scientific and Policy Landscape of Personalized Medicine in Africa- EU-Africa PerMed report

Sela, E., Guinea, J., Radwan, A., Kamau, L., Gitau, E., Nyawira, T., Onsaringo, M., Njambi Musembi, C., Mia, R., Mulima, N., & Moiloa, N. (2021). Mapping the Scientific and Policy Landscape of Personalized Medicine in Africa- EU-Africa PerMed report. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7934221>

The document is openly available for view and downloading at the EU Open Research Repository since the 1st of September 2021. Since then, it has had 305 views and 262 downloads (as per 30/07/2025).

The mapping work carried out by EU-Africa PerMed to review the scientific and policy landscape of PM in Africa has shown that the **African continent must be seen in its diversity and not as a whole when it comes to discuss about health/biomedical research and opportunities for collaboration with Europe.** Many cultural, political, social and economic differences exist between regions and countries in Africa, that influence the opportunities and options for Science, Technology and Innovation (STI) and health research collaboration within Africa and internationally and determine the models and programmes to support and strengthen this collaboration.

The scientific mapping of the African context has shown that over the past decade, there has been a notable increase in the number of research activities and publications in the field of PM across Africa with South Africa and Egypt emerging as the highest contributors, accounting for nearly 50% of all PM publications on the continent. Tunisia, Nigeria, and Kenya followed closely behind, with the top five countries contributing 64.5% of all PM publications in Africa.

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Figure 4: Geographical distribution of Africa’s publications in Personalized Medicine for the period 2011-2020

One major trend in Africa's personalised medicine research landscape is the rapid growth of international collaboration. The proportion of collaborative research jumped from 29% in 2012 to 75% in 2020. European collaboration, as evident by the number of co-authored publications with African countries, increased significantly starting in 2013 and reach its peak in 2019 with more than 350 co-authored publications. Considering the total number of co-authored publications per African region, the patterns of collaboration between major European countries and different African regions has been found to be as follows

- Northern African countries have significant collaboration, especially with France and Italy.
- Western African countries also have notable collaboration, particularly with the UK and Spain.
- Eastern African countries have substantial collaboration with all six European countries but less compared to Northern and Western Africa.
- Southern Africa, represented by South Africa and Malawi, has the highest collaboration with all European countries, especially with the UK and Spain.

The results of the policy mapping have provided valuable information to understand the context and the capacities of African countries to carry out health/biomedical research and specifically in areas that support the development and future implementation of PM in the health systems. The findings have provided a picture of the African countries that shows their level of maturity for the development and implementation of PM, based on their rating for a set of 6 dimensions or capacities: i) governance of health research, ii) financing of health research, iii) resources for health research, iv) health research outputs, v) international collaborations in health research and vi) PM/genomic research. A graphical presentation of the mapping results is shown in the figure below.

Figure 5: Graphical representation of the level of PM/genomic research capacities in African countries, following the mapping framework of EU-Africa PerMed (Ref: Sela E. et al 2021)

THE DIFFERENCES FOUND ACROSS AFRICAN COUNTRIES NEED TO BE CONSIDERED WHEN APPROACHING THE DEFINITION OF ACTIONS TO SUPPORT AND STRENGTHEN THE COLLABORATION IN PM RESEARCH AND INNOVATION BETWEEN AFRICA AND EUROPE.

5.2 POLICY AND SCIENTIFIC IMPACT: EXCHANGE WITH STAKEHOLDERS AND IDENTIFICATION OF NEEDS AND COMMON INTERESTS

Throughout the project, extensive exchanges with and consultation of stakeholders of Africa and Europe through stakeholder workshops and African regional meetings (Western/Central, Northern, Eastern and Southern Africa) have taken place. These meetings have had several objectives that have resulted, at the same time in important project outcomes:

- Collect opinions from African experts about Personalised Medicine, the challenges for Africa, the differences that exist between countries and regions and start the interaction with European experts.
- Contribute to and validate the project work and findings, such as the mapping, the gaps and needs analysis and the Action Plan.
- Support the identification of most relevant topics of interest related to PM for training activities organised by the project.
- Present the ICPeMed and start discussions about the integration of African organisations in the Consortium.
- Seek synergies with on-going projects and programmes that have also the objective of supporting AU-EU collaboration in health research, that are explicitly focusing on PM or that contribute to the AU-EU policy dialogue in STI.

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- Create awareness and visibility about the concept of PM.
- Networking and creation of an EU-Africa PerMed community.

STAKEHOLDER ENGAGEMENT HIGHLIGHTS

TOTAL NUMBER OF STAKEHOLDERS ENGAGED IN PROJECT ACTIVITIES: 1696 individuals.

TOTAL NUMBER OF COUNTRIES REPRESENTED: 86, of which 47 are African countries, 21 from Europe and 18 from the rest of world (se figure below)

Figure 6: Graphical representation of geographic distribution of stakeholders engaged throughout the EU-Africa PerMed project activities

The stakeholder engaged came from the different stakeholder groups, selected as relevant for the project and identified through the stakeholder mapping carried out by the project⁴. Presented below is a graphical representation of typology of stakeholders engaged in % (figure 7).

Figure 7 - Distribution of stakeholder by main group category

⁴ D2.2. Report: [The EU-AFRICA PerMed stakeholder mapping report](#)

The project has organised **3 stakeholder workshops**:

1st Stakeholder Workshop 9-10 February 2022 (online)-

Presentation of Mapping results and collection of perception, challenges and opportunities of PM in Africa. The workshop targeted to have at least 200 participants. This target was almost achieved as **day one had 199 attendees**, while **day two had 137 participants**. Participants were drawn from 43 countries (Figure 6), with 88% coming from the 31 African countries represented.

A **pre-workshop survey** was sent to participants to collect on one hand, general questions about PM, understanding of the concept and the status of implementation in the different countries. At the same time, the survey had questions providing some first input for discussions: PM needs, questions around implementation actions, PM application, collaboration topics, collaboration requirements. This survey provided relevant information to better understand the knowledge of PM in Africa and represented an important baseline to continue the exchanges and collaboration with African stakeholders and to further process the input received during the work of the project.

Based on this first exchange with African stakeholders, EU-Africa PerMed developed further project activities:

- ✓ Organisation of regional meetings: At least one meeting per African region (if possible: in-person or online meetings) organised by EU-Africa PerMed. Recommendation for establishing national pilot committees.
- ✓ To strengthen and foster collaboration between Africa and Europe as well as the different stakeholders in PM and for sharing of knowledge: The first WP5 webinars organised by EU-Africa PerMed were opened for participants from all over the world and focused on relevant areas identified to be of high interest: cancer, Ethics and Regulations in Africa, Start-ups entrepreneurship and Clinical studies in Personalised Medicine.

2nd Stakeholder workshop, Cape Town (South Africa), 19-20 February 2023,

Presentation of the gaps and needs identified for PM in Africa, and discussion on areas of mutual interest and collaboration models. The workshop was a hybrid meeting with **164 attendees** (113 in-person and 51 online). Participants were drawn from 29 countries, with 23 African countries represented. Participants from outside Africa came from Canada, France, Germany, Italy, Spain, and United States of America.

Figure 8- 2nd stakeholder workshop family picture. Cape Town, Feb2023

3rd Stakeholder Workshop, Dakar (Senegal) 26-27 June 2024. Present the EU-Africa PerMed Action Plan, discuss and validate with relevant stakeholders the Actions proposed and next steps to be taken, support African regional consortia. It took place in a hybrid format, with **125 participants** 78 registered onsite and 47 online. In this workshop, there was a high number of participants coming from the stakeholder group of policy makers and funders, both from the area of STI as well as Health, as the meeting was much focused on engaging with those actors that could somehow facilitate the implementation of the Action Plan.

Figure 9- 3rd stakeholder workshop family picture, Dakar, Jun2024

REGIONAL STAKEHOLDER MEETINGS

Based on the results of the mapping work carried out during the first year of the project and the information collected through the first stakeholder workshop and workshop survey, the project opened up a new strategy to approach the engagement and interviews with stakeholder on regional level, i.e. bringing together stakeholders of north, southern, central, west or east Africa each in joint meetings, instead of approaching the analysis at African level. This requires the identification of and engagement with the stakeholders and joining them in common meetings and, beforehand, the development of a common strategy for these interviews to collect efficiently the input needed for the analysis of gaps and needs planned for WP3.

Regional engagements have taken place in all regions but at different level and with different approaches. This is mainly due to the i) availability of partners from only a set of African countries in the consortium (South Africa, Kenya, Tanzania, Senegal and Egypt) so not all regions are represented in the EU-Africa PerMed consortium; ii) already existing linkages between some African and European countries that have facilitated the engagement (the case of North-African francophone countries with close links to France); iii) important differences in the level of development of health/PM research across African countries (as found out by the mapping work) that implies that not all African countries have been considered for the detailed gaps and needs analysis (focusing mainly on those at a certain level of development) and iv) difficulties in identifying and engaging with some relevant stakeholders to attend the organised meetings. Nevertheless, the information collected can be seen as valuable to understand the situation at African regional/country level and to come up with a set of common and important gaps and connected needs for advancing PM development in Africa.

Regional meeting increases also the engagement with African stakeholders, an essential activity for the project to achieve the set objective.

Physical regional meetings were organised for East Africa (Nairobi, Kenya, July 2022) and for Southern Africa (Cape Town, December 2022). Online meetings were organised for the Northern Africa region (9th January 2023) and West-Central Africa (23rd January 2023). In some cases, these regional meetings served as starting points to the launch of national PM groups (for example in Kenya, South Africa, Morocco and Tunisia).

Figure 10: East Africa stakeholder workshop, Nairobi, July 2022

Based on the interaction with stakeholders, and in preparation of the Action Plan, the project identified **broad areas for AU-EU collaboration:**

- i. research on concrete diseases (like cancer, cardiovascular diseases as well as diabetes/metabolic diseases and infectious diseases);
- ii. Development and maintenance of sustainable infrastructure supportive for PM implementation (data repositories, biobanks, analytical platforms, etc.);
- iii. Advocacy and sensitisation efforts directed to policy makers that shall help improving the knowledge base, increase advocacy and in turn help guiding political orientation and
- iv. Education and training activities. A report on gaps and needs assessment in African PM ecosystem has been prepared. The outputs of all regional engagements have initiated regional networking of interested and influential stakeholders that could support the further development of the African PM agenda in each region and foster specific activities to create an African PM strategy with concrete actions for the upcoming years.

The outputs of all regional engagements have fostered regional networking of interested and influential stakeholders that could support the further development of the African PM agenda in each region and foster specific activities to create an African PM strategic roadmap/ action plan. This can be seen as an important outcome of the project that was not initially planned, but that will contribute to advance the PM agenda in some countries and regions, especially for those in that EU-Africa PerMed project partner organisations have their origin (Egypt, Kenya, South Africa and Senegal) (see section 6),

During the regional exchanges, the advantage to develop collaboration with countries of the EU that already advanced in PM was endorsed as Africa has to foster a momentum of research and innovation (R&I) that can drive PM on the continent; develop African specific population genomic knowledge and develop mechanisms to enhance funding; harmonise ethical and legal considerations to enable PM research innovation and implementation; develop R&I programmes in PM from low hanging precise diagnostics; to enhance infrastructure and data as well as biobanking repositories; and address workforce development to reverse the brain drain within the science and innovation sector on the continent.

This regional analysis gave rise to an understanding of the Gaps and specific Needs to be addressed in order to build PM R&I agendas in the five regions of the African continent. It furthermore shows the diverse implementation levels of PM in the different African countries and the 5 regions. This emphasising that it is not possible to propose the same approach for PM research, development and innovation as well as implementation for the entire African continent although the basic elements to establish a PM system of health are similar.

All findings were collected and reported in the following **project deliverables**, available on the project website.

KEY OUTPUTS (WP3)

- **D3.1 “List of African PM needs”:** Outlines the first observations regarding the African needs in the field of PM identified by EU-Africa PerMed through mapping activities in WP2 and collected through direct exchanges with African stakeholders, i.e. the preparatory workshop survey and the 1st Stakeholder Workshop.
- **D3.2 “List of areas of mutual interest between Europe and Africa”:** Outlines the outcome of discussions with African stakeholders regarding areas of mutual interest between Europe and Africa in the field of PM and has stepped further than D3.1 by reflecting not only on the African PM areas of interest but highlighting those areas of interest of Europe from the ICPeMed Action Plan to align the potential for collaboration in the field of PM.
- **D3.3 “Report on gaps-and-needs assessment”:** is primarily focused on the African perspective with a gaps-and-needs assessment, setting the African needs (D3.1) in PM in the context of existing frameworks in the status of the African PM ecosystem. The regional approach enabled structured discussions with the most relevant stakeholders and therewith the development of D3.3 report. EU-Africa PerMed has validated the results hereto presented in D3.3 through the second stakeholder workshop that took place on 20-21 February 2023. (The results of the gap and needs analysis are in the process of being part of a peer-review publication).

All documents are available on the project website: <https://www.euafrica-permed.eu/project-deliverables/>

5.3 POLICY AND SCIENTIFIC IMPACT: THE EU-AFRICA PERMED ACTION PLAN

Developed through extensive input from Consortium members and the Advisory Board, and validated with external stakeholders, the Action Plan is one of the major deliverables of the EU-Africa PerMed project.

The document presents an Action Plan to facilitate, foster and promote collaboration in the field of Personalised Medicine (PM) between Africa and Europe. It includes **26 concrete PM research activities and supporting activities** formulated as recommendations to be implemented at different levels and by different actors, to achieve the objectives set forth by the project:

- Foster, facilitate and encourage joint PM activities, projects and programmes between Africa and Europe,
- Strengthen bilateral European Union and African Union (EU-AU) science, technology and innovation (STI) relations in the area of health, including PM.

It has been prepared based on the findings from the project work, mainly the mapping activities, gaps and needs analysis and stakeholder engagement, with discussions with both African and European experts.

Prior to finalisation, the draft Action Plan was presented at the 3rd Stakeholder Workshop held in Dakar, Senegal, in June 2024. Feedback was gathered through a survey involving key stakeholders from both Africa and Europe, which helped refine and improve the document. This final version, shaped by the collaborative process, was published in October 2024, and shared and disseminated through social networks and in ICPeMed and EP PerMed meetings, both in Europe and in Africa.

The EU-Africa PerMed Action Plan is available for downloading at the **EU Open Research Repository** since 7th Oct 2024. <https://zenodo.org/records/14203893>, Since it was published, it has had 735 views and 550 downloads (As per 30/07/2025).

5.4 POLICY IMPACT: INTEGRATION OF AFRICAN COUNTRIES IN ICPERMED

In order to support the objective of encouraging the integration of non-EU countries in ICPerMed, and following the challenges and scopes defined in the topic "Actions in support of the International Consortium for Personalised Medicine" (H2020 Framework Programme), the EU-Africa PerMed project had the final objective of integrating African countries into ICPerMed activities and the ERA-NET Co-fund for Personalised Medicine (ERA PerMed).

To achieve this objective, EU-Africa PerMed has acted on several different levels:

- I. Presenting ICPerMed, ERA PerMed and the ICPerMed family to the African communities;
- II. Bilateral exchanges with African organisations that could potentially be interested in joining ICPerMed.
- III. Integrating the African perspective in activities on European and international level and particularly those of ICPerMed, ERA PerMed and the ICPerMed family, and lately also in EP PerMed;
- IV. Developing common dissemination and communication activities between EU-Africa PerMed, ICPerMed, ERA PerMed and the ICPerMed family.

In project deliverable D4.3 Report (final) on interactions of EU-Africa PerMed with ICPerMed, ERA PerMed and the Africa-EU Partnership⁵, there is an extensive explanation of all the work done (up to January 2025).

The project was granted a 6-month no cost extension (January-July 2025) to specifically advance in the integration of African organisations in ICPerMed. During this period, the project team had virtual meetings with 11 organisations: Uganda National Council for Science and Technology (NCST), Tanzania Commission for Science and Technology (COSTECH), Ministry of Health and Social Action (MSAS) of Senegal, The Armauer Hansen Research Institute (AHRI) of Ethiopia, the National Council for Science and Technology (NCST) of Malawi, Ministry of Higher Education, Scientific Research and Professional Training/Ministry of health of Morocco, National Council for Science and Technology (NCST) of Rwanda, the East -African Health Research Commission (EAHRC), The East Africa Science and Technology Commission (EASTCO), the AU agency AUDA-NEPAD and the Science for Africa Foundation.

Moreover, the project organised a meeting in Nairobi (Kenya) on the 11-12 June 2025 to advance in the integration of African organization in ICPerMed, where most of these organisations participated, together with members of ICPerMed. The aim of the Engagement Meeting was to bring organisations interested in joining the ICPerMed together to discuss PM in general, the benefits and opportunities coming from global collaborations, and the ICPerMed consortium specifically, and how those joint collaborations can support local, national and regional developments. It will also be a moment of exchange, lessons learnt and sharing of experiences, in which ICPerMed member organisations from Africa, Europe and globally will meet African organisations that still reflect on the ICPerMed membership.

Presented below are the results achieved by the project in terms of contributing the internationalisation of ICPerMed and the presence of African organisations and the African perspective in ICPerMed.

⁵ Document available on the project website <https://www.euafrica-permed.eu/project-deliverables/>

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4 AFRICAN ORGANISATIONS ARE NOW FULL MEMBERS OF ICPeMed.

- South African Medical Research Council (SAMRC) joined in 2022
- Egyptian Academy of Scientific Research and Technology (ASRT) joined in 2023
- Ministry of Higher Education and Scientific Research (MHESR) of Tunisia joined in 2024
- The Tanzania Commission for Science and Technology (COSTECH) joined in 2025

- ✓ Rizwana Mia, from the SAMRC, one of the partners in EU-Africa PerMed is now one of the vice-chairs of ICPeMed.
- ✓ The SAMRC joined the ERA PerMed Joint Transnational Call (JTC)2022. One project, coordinated by a South African research group received funding in the JTC2022.

Julia H. Goedecke

Coordinator:

Julia H. Goedecke, South African Medical Research Council/WITS Developmental Pathways for Health Research Unit (DPHRU), Dept. of Paediatrics, Faculty of Health Sciences, University of the Witwatersrand and Biomedical Research and Innovation Platform, South African Medical Research Council, South Africa

OPTIMA

Omics Approach for Personalised Prevention of Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus for African and European Populations

The global prevalence of type 2 diabetes (T2D) is increasing, with sub-Saharan Africa most affected. Although the development of T2D differs between African and European populations, and between men and women, risk screening and guidelines for the prevention of T2D are generic. This collaboration between Sweden, Germany and South Africa enables the measurement of circulating proteins and metabolites to identify sex- and ethnic-specific biomarkers for the early prediction of T2D risk in two African cohorts (South African and Ghana) and a European (Swedish) cohort. We will also link these biomarkers to dietary patterns, which will be used to inform targeted dietary modifications for primary prevention of T2D in the different populations. The cost effectiveness of the targeted dietary modifications, as well as the perceptions among target populations regarding these early preventative strategies will be assessed in the respective countries to inform future implementation of personalised prevention strategies.

- ✓ Experts from Africa were successfully integrated as reviewers in the JTC2021.
- ✓ The SAMRC joined the EP PerMed Joint Transnational Call (JTC)2025 and has become a partner of the European Partnership since July 2025. This has been possible after joining ICPeMed.

Together with these tangible outputs and outcomes, the project has contributed to a better understanding among the ICPeMed community of the African context for PM, such as:

- **Africa is ready for PM.** The continent has a high-level research community working in PM-related areas, that can compete on equal level with their European peers when it comes to producing scientific knowledge. They could join, if funding was available, multinational research consortia working on PM.

For some countries, there is a need of financial support to increase their R&I capacity in PM and to attain a competitive position.

- **Collaborating with Africa means collaborating with 55 countries.** Africa cannot be seen as a whole because of the existence of substantial economic, cultural, social, environmental and religious differences as well as language barriers between countries even of the same African regions. Moreover, countries are at different levels of development of PM research and implementation.
- **Africa is in a good moment to start discussions about implementing Personalised Medicine.** PM development needs its time and a careful preparation but if carefully prepared and implemented, it can make a healthcare system more efficient. As healthcare systems in a lot of African countries are still under development, the introduction of PM comes at the right moment (can be compared to other technological developments as fixed phone lines instead of passing directly to mobile phones).
- **Africa can greatly contribute to the global PM Agenda.** Channel efforts towards characterizing African Genome, in order to bring to light the genetic diversity of the African population and foster genomics of infectious diseases, are important assets with which the African countries can contribute to the global PM research agenda and include African genomic data in global genetic repositories.
- **Opening the ICPeMed consortium to Africa has benefits for both parts.** African organisations can learn from how European countries have coordinated the research and implementation agenda for PM, already existing good practices, the use of common standards for PM research, the data sharing problems, etc. African organisations bring to the table their knowledge on coping with infectious diseases, the implementation of PM in low resource settings, research groups that are advancing on the knowledge of the genomics variations in the African population (with the highest level of genomic variability) and the importance Africa has to contribute to the ongoing efforts toward global disease prevention and management.

5.5 SCIENTIFIC AND CAPACITY BUILDING IMPACT: CREATING INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC NETWORKS AND ADVANCING YOUNG RESEARCHERS' CAREERS

A scientific community of relevant target stakeholders has been consolidated by the project activities, most specially training and capacity building activities (WP5). This community has been refined, regularly updated and complemented with new contacts identified during the different events and other internal activities by all the consortium members during the project's lifetime. The different target groups have been selected in order to align with the main objectives of the project and its expected impacts.

At the end of the project, the stakeholder contact list was made of a total of 1696 individuals (see page. 12 of this report).

Specifically, training and capacity building activities facilitated the creation of networks between researchers in across countries and continents. A total of 1284 individuals participated in at least, one of training activities carried out during the project (12 webinars and 2 summer schools). Specially the summer schools, which were 2-3 days of training on site, has helped people to get in contact, learn what others are doing and set the basis for future collaborations.

As an example, contacts from participants attending the 1st Summer School in Cape Town have facilitated the collaboration of S. African and Italian researchers in two Horizon Europe Proposals. Paolo Mariotti, from the IRCCS Istituto Romagnolo per lo Studio dei Tumori "Dino Amadori" in Italy contacted Rizwana Mia (SAMRC) and based on this contact, S. African Researchers were invited to join two HorizonEurope project proposals in Cancer and Onco-haematology area.

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Another example of how the project has contributed to support the research career of African students is by networks created from their participation in the project training activities, mainly the summer schools.

African young researchers have had the opportunity to participate in training activities organised by EP PerMed thanks to having joined the project summer schools where they learned about ICPeMed and EP PerMed and contacted with some of their members. This is the case of Abel Anzaku Abbas, PhD student from the Institute of human virology in Nigeria, who was selected to participate with scholarship in the 2nd. Summer school organised by the project in Kenya. He has been selected to virtually participate in the 1st implementation school on personalised Medicine organised by EP-PerMed.

Dr. Abel comments in his social media that his training in the summer school *“was very instrumental in shaping my career as an early career scientist as we had the opportunity to be trained and networked with highly-experienced senior scientist from across Africa and Europe.”* He also highlights that *“Networking is one of the most critical paths of career advancement”*. Ref: <https://shorturl.at/ivvsW>

The project has also supported a request of help from Moroccan bioinformatics students to find European research organization in which they could do an internship in areas related to PM. Dr. Hassan Ghazal, Lab of Genomics and Precision Medicine, School of Medicine, Mohammed VI University of Science and Health, Casablanca, Morocco who has attended two of the project stakeholder workshop requested this support to the project coordinator, who was able to find European research centres willing to have students.

EU-Africa PerMed established, since the very beginning, a very close collaboration with a project that was being implemented in North African countries. This project, called **“The Personalised Medicine in North Africa initiative -PerMediNA”**. It is an international research collaboration focused on Personalised Medicine (PM) implementation in North Africa (Algeria, Morocco and Tunisia) with the collaboration of research institutions in France and in Poland, that officially started in 2022. The project was coordinated by the Institut Pasteur from Tunis. EU-Africa PerMed and PerMediNA have established closed links, organising webinars together and increasing the cross-linkage of researchers from

both projects. PerMediNA's coordinator Dr. Yosr Hamdi has presented their work in EU-Africa PerMed stakeholder workshops, and EU-Africa PerMed coordinator (E. Sela) has participated in PerMediNA meetings, including the closing event in Tunis in September 2024. During this meeting, EU-Africa PerMed received an award in recognition of its contributions to the PerMediNA project, which has significantly advanced Personalised Medicine in North Africa. (<https://www.euafrica-permed.eu/permedina-project-concludes-with-recognition-of-eu-africa-permeds-contributions/>)

All project webinars are compiled in one document that includes a short description of the contents of the webinar and the link to the YouTube Channel (see [https://www.euafrica-permed.eu/wp-content/uploads/2025/01/Webinars-Compilation EU-Africa-PerMed.pdf](https://www.euafrica-permed.eu/wp-content/uploads/2025/01/Webinars-Compilation-EU-Africa-PerMed.pdf))

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5.6 POLICY AND SOCIAL IMPACT: RAISING AWARENESS ABOUT PM IN AFRICA AND THE IMPORTANCE OF INTERNATIONAL COLLABORATION

Raising awareness about PM and the importance of international collaboration has been a key objective throughout the project, that has served to not only promote the participation of African organisations in ICPeMed, but also to advance the PM agenda in African countries and regions. All the stakeholder engagement activities have contributed somehow to this important objective, as well as the project participating in external events or producing relevant policy documents, such as the two policy briefs and the Dakar Declaration on Europe- Africa collaboration in Personalised Medicine, or the active communication in social networks.

A specific WP was devoted to communication and dissemination, with the aim of informing and raising public awareness about PM and to ensure maximum visibility of the project key facts, objectives, activities and findings among stakeholders and the general public at large.

Training, education and awareness raising activities directed at policy makers, clinicians and health care workforce, patients and the general public have been found by the project of being of utmost importance for creating the right conditions for PM to be a reality.

EU-Africa PerMed has contributed with several communication tools to this objective and has greatly supported an increase of interest about PM from the African policy makers groups, including both the research and innovation part, as well as those managing the national health systems.

Listed below are the different communication tools produced by the project:

EU AFRICA Per Med Communication material and tools

Project website <https://www.euafrica-permed.eu/>

Social media: Twitter (@EU_AfricaPerMed)

LinkedIn <https://shorturl.at/RqLkh>

YouTube channel with 24 videos <https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCxhOa0TckWWkPwyAjERIDZw>

Two policy Briefs:

- POLICY BRIEF 1: Opportunities to advance personalised medicine in Africa (<https://zenodo.org/record/7786300#.ZCWvmnZByCl>)
- POLICY BRIEF 2: Sustainable European and African collaboration in Personalised Medicine (<https://zenodo.org/records/15386927>)

7 Project Newsletters: <https://www.euafrica-permed.eu/newsletters/>

2 project flyers (<https://www.euafrica-permed.eu/project-information/>)

6 Success stories of Africa-Europe research collaboration in Personalised Medicine (PM). Through real case examples, the project presented compelling narratives that illustrates the tangible benefits of international collaboration in this field. <https://www.euafrica-permed.eu/success-stories/>

Summary of all the Communication and Dissemination activities are available in project deliverables (<https://www.euafrica-permed.eu/project-deliverables/>):

- D6.2. Report I on Dissemination and Communication Activities (M18)
- D6.3. Report II on Dissemination and Communication Activities (M36)

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Figure 11: EU-Africa PerMed main communication channels: website, newsletters, social media and YouTube channel.

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Figure 12: EU-Africa PerMed appears in different media and serves as an opportunity for press to speak about Personalised Medicine

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HORIZON EUROPE strategic plan | 2025 - 2027

- **Infectious diseases and antimicrobial resistance**, and poverty-related and neglected infectious diseases through the Global Health EDCTP3 Joint Undertaking, which is the third programme of the European and Developing Countries Clinical Trials Partnership (EDCTP). It aims to accelerate the clinical development of new or improved health technology products in sub-Saharan Africa. Global Health EDCTP3 also aims to address antimicrobial resistance in sub-Saharan Africa, taking into consideration the specific environmental and epidemiological factors that influence the spread of antimicrobial resistance in this region. A dedicated Horizon Europe partnership on One Health antimicrobial resistance will specifically address antimicrobial resistance with a One Health approach, by coordinating and aligning activities and funding between the Commission and countries in the EU and beyond.
- **Preparedness and quick response to public health emergencies** supporting the action of the European Health Emergency Preparedness and Response Authority (EHRA) through dedicated partnerships, such as the Horizon Europe pandemic preparedness partnership, and multilateral initiatives, such as the Coalition for Epidemic Preparedness Innovators (CEPI) or the Global Research Collaboration for Infectious Disease Preparedness (GRIID-2).
- **Chronic diseases**, through dedicated actions and multilateral initiatives, such as the Global Alliance for Chronic Diseases (GACD) and the International Rare Diseases Research Consortium (IRDiRC) or the European Partnership on Rare Diseases open to non-EU countries.
- **Personalised medicine**, through dedicated actions and multilateral initiatives, such as the International Consortium for Personalised Medicine (ICPerMed) and linked regional activities such as the **EU-Africa PerMed initiative** between the EU and African countries, the European Partnership on Personalised Medicine (open to non-EU countries) or the International Human Epigenome Consortium (IHEC).
- **Cohort-based clinical studies of health and diseases**, through common approaches and protocols. Impact of the environment on human health, through dedicated actions on the exposome and through cooperation with the WHO European Environment and Health Process.
- **The Latin America and Caribbean initiative**: the Health Cluster will contribute to deepening EU relations with the region of Latin America and the Caribbean (LAC) as part of the LAC initiative under Horizon Europe 2025-2027.
- **The Human Frontier Science Programme** through a dedicated support to this prestigious international programme funding frontier life science research.

US participants in projects funded under the Health Cluster will continue to be eligible for funding, in recognition of the openness of the USA National Institutes of Health (NIH) programme to European researchers.

Hybrid meeting of the EDCTP Association General Assembly (GA) meeting
Thursday, 25 May 2023 (10:00-16:00 CEST)

Building links between Europe and Africa in Personalised Medicine (PM)

- The **EU-Africa PerMed** project has the overall aim of integrating African countries into the International Consortium Personalized Medicine (ICPerMed) activities, thus contributing to a successful implementation of Personalized Medicine (PM) in the global context.
- EU-Africa PerMed: 13 partners, 6 from Europe and 7 from Africa
- ICPerMed: 40 funding bodies from EU member states and beyond, e.g. SAMRC
- It fosters joint PM projects and programmes between Europe and Africa, as well as strengthening bilateral EU-AU science, technology and innovation (STI) relations in the area of health.
- Ongoing activities:
 - Support translation of PM research into praxis by education and training activities directed towards African researchers.
 - Mapping the scientific landscape of PM in Africa, including gaps and needs assessment;
 - Facilitate the integration of African Union countries in the ICPerMed consortium, through the participation of country representatives in workshops, conferences.

<https://confis.europa.eu/project/id/964333>

Relevant activities by DG Research & Innovation

Dashboard of initiatives contributing to the implementation of the AU-EU Innovation Agenda

Click on each initiative's cell to access to its respective website. By leaving your mouse on each budget line, a summary box will pop up, providing overview information on each initiative including contact details.

Type of Action: All

Priority areas	Action title	Initiative	Month/Year of Start	Month/Year of End	Funding Entity	Implementing Entity	Geographic Scope	Budget
		(CoRE), led by ARUA and The Guild	September 2025	2033	participating Universities	universities and non-academic organisations	Africa & Europe	8.83M €
	Designing and implementing new methods and tools to monitor, prevent and counteract future health threats (long standing/re-emerging/antimicrobial resistant pathogens as well as chronic diseases), promoting One Health and precision medicine, in a changing environment, embedding the mental health dimension in this approach.	EU-Africa PerMed: Building links between Europe and Africa in Personalised Medicine	February 2021	January 2025	EU Framework Programme 2014-2020 Horizon 2020	EU-Africa PerMed consortium	Africa & Europe	2,00M €
		Global Health EDCTP3 Joint Undertaking Work Programme 2022, 2023 and 2024	September 2023	January 2031	EU, EDCTP Association and contributing partners	TBD	Africa	389,00M €

Figure 13: EU-Africa PerMed project has been highlighted as a relevant initiative for AU-EU collaboration by the EC (Horizon Europe Strategic Plan 2025-2027), by the EDCTP programme and by the AU-EU Innovation agenda.

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KEY OUTPUTS (WP2 and WP3). POLICY BRIEFS

POLICY BRIEF N° 1: Opportunities to Advance Personalised Medicine in Africa.

The first Policy Brief of the EU-Africa PerMed project presents the findings from the scientific and policy mapping of Personalised Medicine in Africa (PM), and highlights the opportunities that Africa can explore to strengthen the development and implementation of PM. The document also includes a set of Policy Recommendations for African governments, ministries of health, research, science, and technology agencies, as well as regional bodies for advancing the development of PM in African countries, as well as suggestions to solidify the links between Africa and the EU when it comes to PM. Available for view and downloading in <https://zenodo.org/record/7786300#.ZCWvmnZByCl>

Uploaded on ZENODO on 20th April 222. Since it was published, it has had 225 views and 154 downloads. (as of 30 July 2025)

The context and problem

Africa continues to experience a comparatively high burden of disease, particularly infectious diseases such as malaria, HIV/AIDS, and non-communicable diseases like cancer, hypertension, cardiovascular and diabetes, affecting an estimated one billion people (WHO, 2019). According to the World Bank (2020), Africa's disease burden leads to over USD 800 billion in annual productivity loss. There is a need to explore new models and tools for managing the disease burden on the continent. One such model is Personalised Medicine (PM), which refers to a medical model using the characterisation of individual phenotypes and genotypes (e.g., molecular profiling, medical imaging, lifestyle data). This helps in tailoring the right therapeutic strategy for the right person at the right time, determining the predisposition to disease, and delivering timely and targeted prevention (European Commission, 2015).

POLICY BRIEF N° 2: Sustainable European and African Collaboration in Personalised Medicine

This document outlines first-hand lessons learnt for African-European collaborations of the EU-Africa PerMed project (www.euafrica-permed.eu) introduces the "Action Plan to facilitate, foster and promote personalised medicine research collaboration between Europe and Africa", and presents four major recommendations for sustainable collaborations in personalised medicine (PM): 1) Establish funding mechanisms for African-European collaborations on PM research; 2) Create the conditions for an equitable environment for African-European collaborations; 3) Identify and develop PM supporting policies; and 4) Foster the organisation and collaboration at multiple levels to advance PM. The document is addressed to global, regional, and national stakeholders, such as the European Union (EU), African Union (AU), funding bodies, non-governmental organisations (NGOs), and public-private entities. This document emphasises the value of equitable partnerships to advance PM globally. Available for view and downloading at: <https://zenodo.org/records/15386927>

Uploaded on ZENODO on 1st January 2025. Since then, it has had 132 views and 141 downloads (as of 30 July 2025)

EU-Africa PerMed has been funded by the European Union’s Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement Num. 964333

KEY OUTPUTS (WP6) SUCCESS STORIES OF AFRICA-EUROPE COLLABORATION IN PERSONALISED MEDICINE

EU-Africa PerMed has undertaken an initiative to identify and showcase success stories of Africa-Europe research collaboration in Personalised Medicine. Through real case examples, the project presents compelling narratives that illustrate the tangible benefits of international collaboration in this field, offering valuable insights to policymakers, patients, clinicians, and the general public on why such collaborations are essential to support.

Through these success stories, the project aims to inspire further international collaboration and greater support for advancing research in Personalised Medicine.

Figure 14: EU-Africa PerMed 6 success stories of Africa-Europe collaboration in Personalised Medicine

Success stories are available for view and download on ZENODO, the EU Open repository since January 2025.

- **PerMediNA- Personalized Medicine in North Africa (<https://zenodo.org/records/14645103>) Views: 14, Downloads: 26 (as of 30/07/2025)**
- **SALAMA STUDY: Studying Acute Leukaemia Mutations in Africa (<https://zenodo.org/records/14644959>) Views: 12 Downloads: 13 (as of 30/07/2025)**
- **A Two-Decade Collaboration Advancing Pharmacogenetics and Personalised Medicine in Africa (<https://zenodo.org/records/14645054>) Views:10 Downloads:12 (as of 30/07/2025)**
- **ENND The Egyptian Network for Neurodegenerative Diseases. (<https://zenodo.org/uploads/14645252>), Views: 10, Downloads: 16 (as of 30/07/2025).**
- **The OPTIMA project (<https://zenodo.org/uploads/14645176>) Views: 18, Downloads 31 (as of 30/07/2025)**
- **The KEMRI Wellcome Trust Research Programme (KWTRP) (<https://zenodo.org/records/14645207>) Views 8, Downloads.9 (as of 30/07/2025)**

The EU-Africa PerMed success stories are also shown on the ICPeMed and EP PerMed website to increase visibility

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Success Stories for African-European Collaboration in Personalised Medicine published

17 January 2025 – EU-Africa PerMed, a project of the ICPerMed Family, has identified and is showcasing success stories of African-European research collaborations in personalised medicine.

Through real case examples, EU-Africa PerMed presents compelling narratives that illustrate the tangible benefits of international collaboration in personalised medicine and offers valuable insights to policymakers, patients, clinicians, and the general public on why such collaborations are essential to support.

Through these success stories, EU-Africa PerMed aims to inspire further international collaboration and greater support for advancing research in personalised medicine.

1. PerMedINA - Personalised Medicine in North Africa
2. SALAMA study - Studying Acute Leukemia Mutations in Africa
3. African-European pharmacogenetics partnership
4. ENND Egyptian Network for Neurodegenerative Diseases
5. OPTIMA project - Omics Approach for Personalised Prevention of Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus for African and European Populations
6. KEMBI Wellcome Trust Research Programme

[Read all Stories](#)

Figure 15 The ICPerMed and EP PerMed website showing the EU-Africa PerMed success stories of Africa-Europe Collaboration in PM. (<https://www.icpermed.eu/news/success-stories-for-african-european-collaboration-in-personalised-medicine-published/>) (<https://www.eppermed.eu/news-events/news/success-stories-for-african-european-collaboration-in-personalised-medicine-published/>)

KEY OUTPUTS (WP3, WP4 and WP6) THE DAKAR DECLARATION (June 2024)

At the closing ceremony of our 3rd Stakeholder Workshop, EU-Africa PerMed presented the **Dakar Declaration on Europe-Africa Collaboration in Personalised Medicine**. This Declaration is available in **English** and **French**. (<https://www.euafrika-permed.eu/3rd-eu-africa-permed-stakeholder-workshop/>)

Figure 16: Presentation of the Dakar Declaration at the Closing Ceremony of the 3rd Stakeholder Workshop (27 June 2024): Prof. Patrice Debre (Inserm, France), Dr. Ibrahima Sy (Senegalese Ministry of Health and Social Action), Mr. Stephane Devaux (Head of Cooperation, EU Delegation in Senegal), Prof. Soleymane Mboup (IRESSEF, Senegal), Dr. Erika Sela Andres (EU-Africa PerMed Coordinator, Spain), Dr. Ousmane Kane (ANSTS, Senegal), and Dr. Badara Cisse (IRESSEF, Senegal).

The **Dakar Declaration** emphasises the critical role of Personalised Medicine in improving healthcare outcomes for various diseases such as cancer, infectious diseases, diabetes, metabolic disorders, cardiovascular diseases, and mental health. The declaration highlights the importance of supporting research, fostering regional collaborations, and promoting technological innovations. It underscores the necessity for active communication and capacity building to ensure the effective implementation of Personalised Medicine, benefiting both European and African populations through enhanced prevention, diagnosis, and treatment strategies.

6) EU-Africa PerMed ADDITIONAL IMPACTS

This section shows some of the unexpected positive impacts that the EU-Africa PerMed has had, and that were not initially planned nor expected, but that are relevant to show, such as contributing to advancing the PM agenda, at national, regional and Pan-African level. We show the examples of Kenya and Tunisia, and also show activities, not initially planned, but that have also contributed to advancing the PM agenda in Africa, or references of EU-Africa PerMed work by third parties.

The project has also had some positive impacts/effects on European members states and on individual organisations that have participated in the project. We present the example of France (with two organisations participating as partners in the project, ANR and INSERM) and the African Population health Research Centre (APHRC).

6.1 Advancing the PM agenda in Africa.

Supporting the advancement of the PM agenda at national, regional or continental level has been a positive effect that can be attributed to the work carried out by the project and that can be perceived mostly in those countries in which the project had partners (i.e. Kenya, South Africa, Senegal, Egypt), but also in other with which the project has had close collaboration (as the case of Tunisia). The project work has also impacted at regional level (thanks to the regional stakeholder meetings) or Pan-African level (with the participation of AUDA-NEPAD).

South Africa and Egypt both joined the ICPeMed during the first years of the project. In both cases, they had National PM agendas or programmes already on-going, and the integration in ICPeMed was supported by the project) and both countries were on top of the maturity level for PM, as found in the project mapping work. But the project has been an effective tool to boost the PM agenda in other countries in which the concept of PM was still not well understood, specially for policy makers. A good example for this is the case of Kenya, who had two partners in the project: The National Commission for Science, Technology and Innovation (NACOSTI) and the African Population and Health Research Centre (APHRC), and have greatly contributed to the discussions about the opportunities of PM in the country, positioning Kenya now as a clear candidate to shortly join ICPeMed.

The project has been effective in starting the national discussions about PM and creating focus groups in the countries, that have started the engagement of local stakeholders, supporting a better knowledge of PM and the opportunities it may bring to their country, creating awareness about PM among policy makers and more important, starting to create the right environment and context for PM to be a reality in the near future.

Another example of the impacts the projects has had on African countries is the case of Tunisia, which had no partners in the EU-Africa PerMed consortium but has nevertheless benefited from the close interaction that has been established between Tunisian PM stakeholders and the project, since the very beginning of the project.

The project has also had an impact on the definition and discussions towards defining an Africa PM agenda and has also benefited the development of PM research agendas in European member states, as is the case of France.

Presented below are short description of these additional impacts. They show how Coordination and Support Actions such as EU-Africa PerMed can deliver important outcomes and impacts, measurable short-term effects as well as broader and long-term effects. It shows the value of networking and cooperation when it comes to support and strengthen international research collaborations.

EU-Africa PerMed has provided the grounds for a stronger and more sustainable Africa-Europe cooperation in PM. It has created favourable contexts and opportunities for networking and discussion, to share concepts and ideas and for all major stakeholders to be convinced of the gains that this collaboration has for both parts, Africa and Europe.

Example 1- Impacts on Kenya and East Africa region

Since the start of the EU-Africa PerMed project and the various stakeholder engagements and project outputs, Kenya has witnessed a tremendous increase in interest on precision medicine. From a point where the topic was not very familiar, it’s now become a frequent term in health policy and research related fora. There has also been increased PM related activities in the country some of which are indicated below:

1. Advancing the creation of national/regional PM task forces

Kenya has already created a think tank to spearhead development of PM in the country.

https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=AOWwZXAQ6sM&ab_channel=KBCChannel1

2. Promoting stakeholder discussions on PM in the country

<https://www.kemri.go.ke/unveiling-kenyas-precision-medicine-strengthening-disease-management-through-targeted-therapy/>

3. New PM programme/initiative in the country

The EU- Africa project partners from Kenya and representatives of the task force with the support of the Principal Secretary – Research, Science and Innovation are in the process of developing a national PM strategy and supporting guidelines.

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4. Publications/news

Some of the authors ([Clarisse Musanabaganwa](#), [Francis Makokha](#) and [Jean Baptiste Mazarati](#)) of the paper referenced below were among those who had been invited as speakers during the East Africa PM stakeholder meeting held in 2022, and which was organised by the EU-Africa PerMed Project. The paper was published an year later, and included an assessment of some of the PM gaps identified during the meeting.

Musanabaganwa, C., Ruton, H., Ruhangaza, D., Nsabimana, N., Kayitare, E., Muvunyi, T. Z., Semakula, M., Ntirenganya, F., Musoni, E., Ndoli, J., Hategekimana, E., Nassir, A., Makokha, F., Uwimana, A., Gasana, J., Munezero, P. C., Uwinkindi, F., Muvunyi, C. M., Nyirazinyoye, L., Mazarati, J. B., ... Mutesa, L. (2023). An Assessment of the Knowledge and Perceptions of Precision Medicine (PM) in the Rwandan Healthcare Setting. *Journal of personalized medicine*, 13(12), 1707. <https://doi.org/10.3390/jpm13121707>

Example 2. Impacts on Tunisia

NOTE: The following text on the impacts and benefits gained by Tunisia, as a country, as results of the collaboration of relevant Tunisian stakeholders in the project has been prepared by Dr. Helmi Mardassi, Director General, Unit for the Management of the UE R&I framework programme Horizon Europe, Interim Director General of Research Valorization. Ministry of Higher Education and Scientific Research, Tunisia

No organisation from Tunisia participated directly as partners in the EU-Africa PerMed consortium, so these are impacts from the project, clear effects that can be attributed to the project work and have benefited the development of PM in Tunisia.

Tunisia has taken substantial steps toward advancing Precision Medicine (PM), both nationally and internationally. Through the strategic integration of genomic technologies and active participation in global initiatives, the country has positioned itself as a regional leader in PM.

A flagship example of this effort is the PerMediNA project, which demonstrated the potential of regional collaboration and capacity-building in the Mediterranean context. In parallel, Tunisia institutionalized a National Genomic and Precision Medicine Center, built on inter-ministerial collaboration (Ministries of Health, Higher Education and Scientific Research, and the Ministry of Finance)

Tunisia's adhesion to the International Consortium for Personalised Medicine (ICPerMed) in November 2024—further catalysed these efforts. This international integration has fostered knowledge transfer, joint research participation, and high-level training for emerging experts in the field.

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Tunisian policymakers have actively participated in EU-Africa PerMed’s high-level strategic meetings (e.g., The 5th ICPerMed Workshop in Sienna, in Nov 2023), reinforcing national momentum toward implementing PM. (see post on social networks on the left corner)

Tunisian representatives participated in multiple EU-Africa PerMed events (3rd Stakeholder workshop in Dakar, June 2023 and the ICPerMed engagement meeting in Nairobi, June 2025), which served as a catalyst for these national dialogues, and who benefited from EU-Africa PerMed Network documents and collaboration opportunities to different parties.

Additionally, multiple expert workshops and stakeholder consultations were held at the national level with universities, clinicians, researchers, and decision-makers to explore the integration of PM in Tunisia’s health system.

PerMediNA played a key role in building strong networks with partners from both Europe and the rest of Africa. The PerMediNA team participated in the EU-Africa PerMed Summer School, further strengthening cross-continental collaboration and knowledge exchange. From another side the project PI of EU-Africa PerMed Project was among the invited speakers at the PerMediNA final meeting. EU-Africa PerMed and PerMediNA have jointly organised

an excellent webinar on Functional Genomics, featuring two internationally recognised speakers from Canada and Japan. The event attracted over 150 participants from across African and European countries, reflecting the growing interest and engagement around this critical field of research.

Members of EU-Africa PerMed and PerMediNA are currently working on ensuring the sustainability of their cooperation by laying the groundwork for a new project proposal to be submitted under the Horizon Europe Programme. Notably, a post-doctoral PerMediNA researcher and a senior team member took part in the EU-Africa PerMed Summer School, further deepening scientific collaboration between Africa and Europe.

Tunisia’s involvement in the EU-Africa PerMed initiative has provided several significant advantages. It has granted access to joint European-African research calls and relevant policy tools, enabling deeper engagement in the continent’s biomedical innovation agenda. The country has been actively integrated into policy-shaping dialogues, allowing it to contribute to and benefit from the strategic direction of precision medicine development. Institutional collaborations have been strengthened, fostering closer ties with European and African partners. Moreover, Tunisia has benefited from capacity-building opportunities through the exchange of best practices, further enhancing its scientific and technical capabilities. This participation has also increased Tunisia’s visibility on international platforms. Altogether, these advancements support Tunisia’s broader ambition to make precision medicine more accessible, sustainable, and adapted to local needs. Tunisia’s strategic alignment with the international PM agenda—underpinned by its EU-Africa PerMed membership and its ICPerMed integration—has enabled key structural, scientific, and training-related achievements.

Example 3: Activities carried out for supporting the African PM Agenda

Participation in the EDCTP Scientific Forum (Oct 2021)

EU-Africa PerMed participated in the 10th EDCTP Scientific Forum that took place in October 2021, with a Sponsored symposium titled: *Fostering a stronger collaboration in Personalised medicine: The EU-Africa PerMed project.* The symposium took place as a Virtual format on the 19th October 2021. The EDCTP Forum is a biennial event that provides an international platform for the presentation and discussion of cutting-edge research addressing the burden of poverty-related infectious diseases in sub-Saharan Africa and the capacity development and networking activities that support this goal. The EDCTP Forum attracts a diverse audience,

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including representatives from research institutions and universities, the larger scientific community, health care providers, governments, regional bodies, regulators, civil society, and public and private research and development partners.

1.4 Sponsored symposia	
TRACK D: Capacity strengthening, collaborations, enhancing the research environment, knowledge translation	
Fostering a stronger collaboration in personalised medicine: The EU-Africa PerMed project	13:00-14:00
Organiser(s):	Instituto de Salud Carlos III (ISCIII, Spain)
Chair(s):	Joaquin Guinea (Spain) and Souleymane Mboup (Senegal)
Presentation(s):	<p>The EU-Africa PerMed project Joaquin Guinea, InnovaTec (Spain)</p> <p>The Personalised Medicine research and innovation landscape in Africa: results of the EU-Africa PerMed scientific and policy mapping work Erika Sela, InnovaTec (Spain) and Amr Radwan, Egyptian Center of Innovation and Technology Development (ECITD, Egypt)</p> <p>Challenges and opportunities of personalised medicine for Africa Rizwana Mia, South African Medical Research Centre (South Africa)</p>

During this symposium the **EU-Africa PerMed** project was presented, explaining its objectives, planned activities and expected results. We also shared with the audience the results of the scientific and policy mapping of PM in Africa carried out, showing what is Africa publishing in PM, in what areas and who are the main actors, together with an overview of the policy landscape supporting R&I in PM. The symposium included a presentation of what can PM offer to fight against main health challenges of the African population and why international collaboration in this area is important.

Example 4: References of EU-Africa PerMed work by third parties

References to our mapping results in external publications.

Some of the reference materials during a consultative meeting organised by Africa CDC on setting the continental agenda for genomic medicine and precision public health in Africa held in September 2024, came from the EU-Africa PerMed project outputs. Attached is a slide taken during one of the presentations.

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The **EU-Africa PerMed Action Plan** has been used by experts in their presentations in external events, as is the case of a presentation by Prof Michele Ramsay, during the Africa CDC Webinar Series on Harnessing the Power of Human Genomics to Transform Healthcare in Africa (26/June/2025) where she reflected on how human genomics can shape the future of precision public health in Africa. She mentioned the EU-Africa PerMed Action Plan as documents that can support the development of genomics and PM in Africa.

Figure 15- Africa CDC Webinar Series on Harnessing the Power of Human Genomics to Transform Healthcare in Africa. Thursday 26th June 2025 at 13:00 East African Time.

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=BihY98WkHmw>

Participation of EU-Africa PerMed in external webinars for African Policy makers.

AUDA-NEPAD through the Calestous Juma Executive Dialogue (CJED) Webinar Series, hosted a webinar under the theme **“Unlocking Africa's Genetic Potential: Exploring Genomics, Gene Editing and Precision Medicine for Transformation”**.

This webinar series aims to underscore the crucial role of scientific priority setting in catalysing research and development (R&D) as well as fostering innovation throughout Africa. By highlighting the significance of genomics, precision medicine and gene editing in enhancing the overall health outcomes of Africa’s population. The webinar is designed to galvanise conversations and strengthen the capacity of senior policy and decision-makers to provide technical advice to governments in assessing and harnessing emerging technologies in their respective institutions and organisations. Other target audience include researchers, the private sector, civil society organisations and all stakeholders towards addressing Africa’s health and development needs.

Members of EU-Africa PerMed were invited to participate in this webinar

Ref: <https://shorturl.at/xOSpl>

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6.2 –Impact on European member states

Personalised medicine as a concept was already considered in France before the launch of the EU-Africa PerMed project. The main impact for France is expected to result from the networking opportunities, i.e. the project has supported the connection of French actors with organisations and individual experts of Africa, starting with the project team members INSERM and ANR, but also other French teams/experts that are predominately of the research and clinical sector. This may result in the future in more collaboration between French and African teams on policy and research level.

Furthermore, though EU-Africa PerMed, already running collaborations financially supported by France were promoted and even recognised as Best Practise: <https://www.euafrica-permed.eu/permedina-2/>

Overall, through the participation in the EU-Africa PerMed project, France has gained more visibility as major actor in the field of personalised medicine in Africa and may benefit of new and strengthened collaboration between French and African teams around research and policy exchanges in the near future.

First discussions were initiated to further support African/French research collaborations dedicated to personalised medicine or personalised medicine supporting aspects.

6.3 Impact on individual organisations

Participating in a project such as EU-Africa PerMed also has a positive impact in the participating organisations, not only in terms of capacity building and learning, but also in gaining international visibility and creating networks, that stay further on the project duration. This has been particularly important for African organisations, such as the case for the South African Medical research Councils (now a full member of ICPeMed and EP PerMed), who has gained visibility within the European Commission and has participated in several meetings representing the country and an example of how participating in this projects is beneficial for not only the organisations but also for the country.

Another example is the **African Population Health Research Center (APHRC)**, based in Nairobi, Kenya. The APHRC is one of the partners in EU-Africa PerMed. It is a premier research-to-policy institution, generating evidence, strengthening research and related capacity in the African research and development ecosystem, and engaging policy to inform action on health and development (<https://aphrc.org/who-we-are/>).

Some of the positive impacts that the project has had for them is presented below, with direct input from the APHRC team.

New Research Collaborations and Capacity Development

Following the EU-Africa PerMed events in South Africa in 2023, new collaborations were initiated between APHRC's Marta Vicente-Crespo and researchers: Mohamed Zahir - Muhimbili University of Health and Allied Science, Michèle Ramsay - Sydney Brenner Institute for Molecular Bioscience at the University of the Witwatersrand, Rokhaya Ndiaye Diallo - Cheikh Anta Diop University, Ghada El-Kamah - Human Genetics and Genome Research Institute at the National Research Centre, and Yosr Hamdi - Institut Pasteur de Tunis at the University of Tunis.

This group has since co-authored a manuscript focused on PM in Africa, leveraging multidisciplinary expertise and regional representation. Currently under review, the co-authored manuscript represents one of the tangible outputs of EU-Africa PerMed's networking efforts. It brings a continental lens to PM and reflects on ethical, infrastructural, and technical bottlenecks identified during PerMed's convenings.

Additionally, a small writing retreat, supported by APHRC's partnership with Queen Mary University of London researcher, Isabel Palacios, further strengthened this collaboration and catalysed ongoing grant fundraising to support work in bioinformatics, genomics, and functional genetics research in Africa.

Policy Advocacy and Ethical Governance

Ongoing discussions are underway between APHRC and the National Commission for Science, Technology and Innovation (NACOSTI) in Kenya to explore a framework to strengthen the governance and ethics review

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capacity for emerging issues in health research, with Personalised Medicine as a priority area. This policy-influencing effort, co-led by APHRC’s and EU-Africa PerMed team member, Rita Karoki, builds directly on insights and momentum from EU-Africa PerMed engagements. While the initiative is not yet funded, it has sparked critical inter-agency dialogue on bioethics and PM integration.

Promotion of Stakeholder Discussions on Personalised Medicine

APHRC, through the Afrique Research Support Hub (ARSH), recently organised a webinar titled **“Personalised Medicine in Africa”** on July 24, 2025. The session drew diverse stakeholders, including researchers, policy influencers, and programme implementers. It featured Mohamed Zahir, a Biomedical Scientist from Muhimbili University of Health and Allied Sciences, a Genetic Counselor, and a passionate Science Communicator. The connection between APHRC and Mohamed was fostered through EU-Africa PerMed. The webinar served as a platform to deepen discourse on Africa’s opportunities and challenges in PM.

Enhancing Long-Term Access to EU-Africa PerMed Webinar Resources

As part of efforts to sustain knowledge sharing beyond live events, APHRC is developing a structured learning pathway on PM on its [Virtual Learning Academy](#) platform. This initiative curates webinars organised by the Consortium between 2022 – 2025. The webinar resources will be integrated into an open-access learning module for wider dissemination through platforms like ARSH. The effort ensures continued access to high-quality PM content, advancing APHRC’s role in promoting equitable and context-specific health innovation across the continent. The effort is expected to be completed by mid-August 2025, and the link will be shared.